

KEY INDICATORS

With 2,675,331 hectares, Spain had the second-largest organic farmland area in the European Union, after France. In terms of organic area share, its 11.0% share was slightly above that of the European Union. Growth from 2001-2022 was almost sixfold and thus higher compared to most EU countries. With 2,655 million euros in 2022, Spain had the sixth-largest organic market in the European Union. 2.5 percent of all food sales were organic.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)	485,079 ha (1.9%)	2,675,331 ha (11%)
Area Growth from 2001 to 2022	452%	

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)	153,851 ha (1.3%)	574,116 ha (4.8%)
Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)	131,904 ha (2.7%)	809,958 ha (16.1%)
Grassland* (Share of Total)	N/D	1,291,257 ha (17.4%)
Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)	N/D	4,023 t (1.5%)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2021

Producers (Share of Total)	15,607 (1.2%)	56,024 (6.1%)
Aquaculture Producers	N/D	173
Processors	914	5,773
Importers	25	498

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)	170 M€	2,655 M€ (2.5%)
Per Capita Consumption	4.2 €	55.8 € (2021)
Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022	1,462%	
Imports	N/D	87,802 t

Source: FIBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN SPAIN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat, Ministry of Agriculture Spain, Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN SPAIN

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Ministry of Agriculture, national data sources

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Spain CAP strategic plan provides for a 20% increase in supported organic area and expenditure by 2027 compared with 2018, when less than half the certified organic area was supported, due mainly to regional differences in support. Planned maintenance payments from 2023 are reduced, in some case substantially, or similar to the previous period. Conversion payments are either similar to maintenance or higher by 10 or 20% depending on region in both periods. As a result of the planned reductions in payments per ha, total expenditure is planned to be 6% higher and average expenditure per ha to fall by 12%. A substantial proportion of certified organic production could remain unsupported.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	1,045 kha	1,257 kha (+20%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	4.3 %	5.1% (+19%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	47%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	159 M€	169 M€ (+6%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	152 €	134 € (-12%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	819 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	5,553 M€	11.1%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	1,837 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	34,169 M€	2.4%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES	OLIVES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	45-450	81-894	128-1,200	75-934	75-900	75-354
	2023	P2	50-433	93-477	127-1,530	122-900	199-996	167-406
Change from 2019 to 2023			~0%	<0%	~0%	~0%	~0%	<0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	41-450	30-853	41-1,561	60-900	60-900	60-534
	2023	P2	55-277	81-400	124-1,530	110-900	129-916	153-364
Change from 2019 to 2023			<0%	<0%	<0%	~0%	~0%	<0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019	P2	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%
	2023	P2	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%	0-20%

Ranges shown as significant variations within category by region, crop and irrigation

Fund: P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Spain has no current national organic action plan. Although one was anticipated in late 2023, it did not materialise following the elections that year. Some regional action plans exist or have existed, illustrated here by an example from Andalusia. In 2020, Andalusia accounted for 1.1 Mha, or 45% of Spanish organic land area.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2016-20	None	None
Current Action Plan	None	None	None

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (ANDALUCIA)

- Consolidate growth; strengthen financial and environmental performance; support for aquaculture; support for women's engagement in organic farming including property rights
- Investment aids for farm improvement, young farmers, processing; improve marketing, supply chain development, producer groups; support consumption in schools, social institutions, restaurants and catering; strengthen control system, Council for Organic Production and SIPEA information system
- Improve knowledge of production methods; support consumption and non-commercial horticulture; develop advisory services, technical publications and web platform; develop training for advisers, farmers; specific studies on technical problems, sustainability and financial performance, technical support for monitoring, evaluation of action plan; support for price and market data in CAPDER observation centre

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (NONE)

- PRODUCTION**: No current plan
- MARKETS**: No current plan
- INFORMATION**: No current plan

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Spain was 2.7% in 2020. Spain provided support for organic aquaculture, including conversion and certification, processing, promotion and packing, as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAR (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.